

Effect of Job Evaluation Techniques on Employee's Salary Structure in Organisation, South East, Nigeria

Authored by

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of job evaluation techniques on employees' salary structure in organizations in Nigeria. Specifically, the study adopted employee skills and working conditions as an independent variable while the organizational salary structure serves as a dependent. A descriptive cross-sectional research design was adopted for the study. The responders were selected at random from among the numerous corporate divisions, including the procurement, finance, and human resources divisions. Purposive sampling was used to choose these organizations for the investigation. The survey findings were evaluated using SPSS 28.0's simple linear regression analysis. The study revealed that employee skills have significantly positively improved the organizational salary structure of organizations with a P-value of (0.019) which is lower than the significance value of 5%. While working conditions have not significantly improved the organizational salary structure of the organizations with the P-value of (0.249) which was higher than the significance value of 5%. We concluded that job evaluation techniques have a significant effect on employees' salary structure in organizations in Nigeria. We recommended that organizations in Nigeria and beyond should endeavor to significantly improve the organizational job evaluation techniques since it has a significant effect on employees' salary structure in organizations in Nigeria.

Keywords: Job Evaluation Techniques; Employee's Salary Structure; Employee Skills

Introduction

The productivity of any organization or enterprise to a large extent depends, on the morale and motivation of its employees. One of the principal factors affecting this is the “pay policy” and “pay structure” of the organization. Paying employees less than the work they perform generates dissatisfaction leading to low morale. Additionally, the hidden cost of paying employees more than necessary also is not desirable. It is wasteful on a common-sense level, but it is even more harmful because of its impact on employees who see other employees doing jobs with less responsibility and being paid more than what is perceived as fair. This feeling could lead to frustration and lower morale and hence productivity loss. An organization needs a system that will attempt to prevent such situations when developed and resolve them to the satisfaction of all concerned.

Job evaluation is a systematic process used to determine the relative worth of different jobs within an organization. It is a critical component of an organization's human resource management, which helps to ensure that employees are fairly compensated for their skills, experience, and contributions to the organization. Job evaluation techniques used in organizations in Nigeria range from traditional methods such as ranking and classification to modern methods such as point factor and factor comparison. However, the extent to which these job evaluation techniques affect employees' salary structure in organizations

Job evaluation is a crucial point in human resources management. The aim of human resources management is to link employees with their work results which should meet in order for an organization to fulfill its tasks. Thus, job evaluation occurs as an irreplaceable factor that enables management through learning the necessary values. Enhancing the efficiency of a company depends on various endogenous and exogenous factors. Job evaluation may be the aspect that tips the scales in your competition's favor. The evaluation itself is an analysis and assessment of requirements aiming at a valuation of job quality (Adamus, 2009). Human resource management is an important area in an organization yet it is very complex because it involves human beings who are intelligent to think, react and act according to their thoughts. Therefore, managing human beings requires skills and expertise so they can fulfill their jobs. For employees to fulfill their job efficiently and effectively, job evaluation is an important human resource practice to determine the value or worth of a particular job in comparison with other jobs (Masanja, 2019).

Statement of the Problem

Job evaluation is a process used by organizations to determine the relative value of different jobs within the organization. It is used to establish fair pay and benefits for employees, and to ensure that the organization is using its resources effectively. The research problem is the discrepancy in the salary of employees of the same organization with the same work schedule. The remuneration structure has always been a problem among employees in various organizations. While some feel they should be paid according to their academic qualifications, others look at skills while some consider productivity. All these factors fall under job evaluation, hence the need to conduct proper job evaluation before preparing salary structure. While job evaluation techniques can be helpful, there are several other potential problems that can arise such as inadequate working conditions and a lack of employee skills. Overall, job evaluation techniques can be helpful in establishing fair pay and benefits for employees, but they can also be prone to a range of problems and limitations. It is important for organizations to carefully consider these issues when designing and implementing job evaluation systems.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to assess the Effect of job evaluation techniques on employees' salary structure in organizations in Nigeria. The specific objectives are;

- i. To investigate the effect of employee skill on the organizational salary structure.
- ii. To examine the effect of working conditions on the organizational salary structure.

Hypotheses of the Study

- i. Employee skill has no significant positive effect on the organizational salary structure.
- ii. Working conditions have no significant positive effect on the organizational salary structure.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Job Evaluation

Job evaluation is one the simplest however critical in nature. One of the basic approaches in job evaluation is ranking. Ranking involves comparing jobs to each other based on the overall worth of a job to an organization (Mansaja, 2019). Job evaluation is a mainstream tool for everyone involved in Human Resource and Personnel Management. It is a systematic way of determining the relative value of various jobs in an organization (Binghay, 2022). Job evaluation is a process whereby jobs are placed in rank order according to overall demands placed upon the job holder. It, therefore, provides a basis for a fair and orderly grading structure (Pandey and Leelashree, 2012). According to Kimball and Kimball, "Job evaluation represents an effort to determine the relative value of every job in a plant and to determine what the fair basic wage for such a job should be. Job evaluation does not determine actual pay. It is a technique of job analysis, assessment, and comparison and it is concerned with the demands of the job, such as the experience and the responsibility required to carry out the job. It is not concerned with the total volume of work, the number of people required to do it, the scheduling of work, or the ability of the job holder (Pandey and Leelashree, 2012).

The worth of a job is normally on the judgment of knowledge, effort, accountability, and working conditions involved in the job execution. Some of the advantages of ranking include simplicity in the application of job evaluation and it is very effective for a few jobs to be evaluated (Mansaja, 2019). The use of job evaluation systems in the private sector increased during World War II. Under wage and price controls, the War Labor Board permitted upward pay adjustments only when job evaluation data demonstrated inequities in the pay structure (Gupta, 1991). Job evaluation is the process of establishing a structure for jobs in an organization. The concern for job evaluation is not for people, but for the job itself (IvyPanda, 2020).

Specifically, it is normally most suitable for less than 30 jobs in the organization. On the other hand, the shortcoming involves difficulty to administer a large number of jobs. In case the job increases, then it would be difficult to evaluate. In addition, the ranking system is subjective in nature. This is because there is no standard used for comparison. It means new jobs would have to be compared with the existing jobs to determine the appropriate ranks (Mansaja, 2019). The following are the objectives of job evaluation: determining how much people who perform the job, should be paid, means of comparing jobs, and pay rates with those of other organizations (IvyPanda, 2020).

Job evaluation is a process of determining the relative worth of a job. It is a process that is helpful even for framing compensation plans by the personnel manager. Job evaluation as a process is advantageous to a company in many ways:

1. **Reduction in Inequalities in Salary Structure** - It is found that people and their motivation are dependent upon how well they are being paid. Therefore, the main objective of job evaluation is to have external and internal consistency in salary structure so that inequalities in salaries are reduced.
2. **Specialization** - Because of the division of labor and thereby specialization, a large number of enterprises have got a hundred jobs and many employees to perform them. Therefore, an attempt should be made to define a job and thereby fix salaries for it. This is possible only through job evaluation.

3. **Helps in the Selection of Employees** - The job evaluation information can be helpful at the time of selection of candidates. The factors that are determined for job evaluation can be taken into account while selecting the employees.
4. **Harmonious Relationship Between Employees and Managers** - Through job evaluation, harmonious and congenial relations can be maintained between employees and management so that all kinds of salary controversies can be minimized.
5. **Standardization** - The process of determining the salary differentials for different jobs becomes standardized through job evaluation. This helps in bringing uniformity into the salary structure.
6. **Relevance of New Jobs** - Through job evaluation, one can understand the relative value of new jobs in a concern (Pandey and Leelashree, 2012).

From a practical point of view, ranking involves ordering, weighing, and paired comparison. Ordering involves placing job titles in an index card and then arranging the order of the job titles according to their relative importance and contribution toward achieving organizational performance. Weighing involves assigning weights depending on several characteristics of the job. Paired comparison is a deliberate comparison of similar job titles. After ranking or grouping has been completed, then determine the appropriate salary for each group or rank. Sometimes, it is easier to use interactive ranking programs to provide an appropriate ranking system for the organization.

There are several methods to conduct a job evaluation. Some of the common methods is Factor comparison and point method

Factor Comparison Method

Factor comparison refers to a set of compensable factors which identify and determine the worth or value of a job. Specifically, the number of compensable factors is small. These factors normally include the following:

1. Skills
2. Responsibilities
3. Effort
4. Working conditions

The following step is to benchmark the determined jobs. This activity of benchmarking should involve certain attributes:

1. Fair or equitable pay: this should not be under or overcompensated.
2. Range of the factors: this requires that each factor whereby some jobs would be at the lowest end or point of the factor and at the same time other jobs would be at the higher end of the factor.

The next step is to price the jobs and the total pay for each job is divided into pay for each factor. Normally, this process determines the rate of pay for each factor for each benchmark job. The occasional adjustment will be made in the matrix to determine equitable shillings weighting of the factors. At the time other jobs in the organizations should be compared to the benchmark jobs and rates of pay for every factor will be summed to identify the rates of pay for each of the other jobs.

The benefit of this method is that the worth of the job is described in monetary terms. Furthermore, this method can be applied to various types of jobs. Ultimately, this method can be used for newly created jobs. On the contrary, the disadvantages include the pay for each factor being by the judgment and opinion of pay evaluators which might

be subjective. In connection with this, the standard applied for determining the pay for every factor might be biased. The business might affect a specific group of employees.

Point Method

The point method refers to a set of compensable factors which determine the value or worth of jobs. The point method is the most widely used. Under this procedure, subject matter experts identify job dimensions that will be the basis for assigning salary levels. These dimensions—known as commensurable factors—are then described in terms of behaviors typical of different levels of skill and assigned a number that reflects differences in skill levels. Jobs can then be scored in terms of the number of points and compared to each other to determine salary level (Smither, 2004). Specifically, the compensable factors include the major categories:

1. Skills
2. Responsibilities
3. Effort
4. Working conditions

Salary Structure

Salary Structure is the structure or details of the salary being offered in terms of the breakup of the various components that constitute the compensation. Salary Structure is the set of parameters that define the salary. Salary structure is very important information that determines the in-hand pay, gross salary, net salary, allowances, etc. All these variables are paid to the employee as a part of his/her compensation and benefits. If an employee does not have details of the components, he/she cannot calculate the in hand as well as savings parts like Employee Provident Fund. (RF) A pay structure is a procedure of administering its pay philosophy. There are different types of pay structures, for example, internal equity method and market pricing. The purpose of a pay structure is to take the role of each person and the reason why people receive different compensation. It also deals with opportunities for incentives (IvyPanda, 2020).

The compensation awarded to the employee is dependent on the volume of effort exerted, the nature of the job, and his skill. Besides, there are several other internal and external factors affecting compensation.

The factors affecting employee compensation can be categorized into:

1. Internal Factors
2. External Factors.

Some of the external factors affecting employee compensation are:

1. Demand and Supply of Labour; 2. Cost of Living; 3. Economic Conditions; 4. Prevailing Wage Level; 5. Society; 6. Government Control; 7. Labour Unions 8. Legislation 9. Globalization 10. Cross-Sector Mobility and 11. Compensation Survey.

Some of the internal factors affecting employee compensation are:

1. Compensation Policy of the Organization 2. Employer's Affordability 3. The worth of a Job 4. Employee's Worth 5. Organizational ability to pay 6. Job Analysis and Job Description and 7. Employee-Related Factors. There are so many factors that contribute to the salary structure of employees. The most important factors which affect individual differences in wage rates are:

- (i) Worker's capacity.

- (ii) Educational qualifications.
- (iii) Work experience.
- (iv) Hazards involved in work.
- (v) Promotion possibilities.
- (vi) Stability of employment.
- (vii) Demand for special skills.
- (viii) Profits or surplus earned by the organization.

Theoretical Framework

Theory-Driven Evaluation Theory

Huey Chen is one of the main contributors to Theory-Driven Evaluation. His approach focuses on the theory of change and causal mechanisms underlying the program. Chen recognizes that programs exist in an open system, consisting of inputs, outputs, outcomes, and impacts. He suggests that evaluators should start by working with stakeholders to understand the assumptions and intended logic behind the program. A logic model can be used to illustrate the causal relationships between activities and outcomes. Chen offers many suggestions for constructing program theory models, such as the action model (i.e. systematic plan for arranging staff, resources, and settings to deliver services) and change model (i.e. set of descriptive assumptions about causal processes underlying intervention and outcome). Evaluators should consider using this approach when working with program implementers to produce valuable information for formative program improvement (Chen, 2015).

Jennifer Greene developed Values Engaged Evaluation (VEE) as a democratic approach that is highly responsive to context and emphasizes stakeholder values. VEE seeks to provide contextualized understandings of social programs that have particular promise for underserved and underrepresented populations (Greene, 2011). It is considered a “democratic” approach because it encourages the evaluator to include all relevant stakeholder values. Greene offers three justifications for including stakeholder values: (1) pragmatic (i.e. increases the chance of use), (2) emancipatory (i.e. empowers stakeholders), and (3) deliberative (i.e. considers all interests). With this approach, evaluation design and methodology evolve as the evaluator understands the context, needs, and values underlying the program. VEE is concerned with answering broad and in-depth questions and is more suited for formative rather than summative evaluations (Greene, Boyce, and Ahn, 2011).

Empowerment Evaluation Theory

David Fetterman developed Empowerment Evaluation as an approach to foster program improvement through empowerment and self-determination (Fetterman, 2012). Self-determination theory describes an individual's agency to chart his or her course in life and the ability to identify and express needs. Fetterman believes the evaluator's role is to empower stakeholders to take ownership of the evaluation process as a vehicle for self-determination. The evaluator engages a diverse range of program stakeholders and acts as a “critical friend” or “coach” while guiding them through the evaluation process. Empowerment evaluation seeks to increase the probability of program success by providing stakeholders with the tools and skills to self-evaluate and mainstream evaluation within their organization. Fetterman outlines three main steps for conducting empowerment evaluation: (1) Develop and refine the “mission,” (2) take stock and prioritize the program's activities, and (3) plan for the future.

Empirical Review

Rizwan, et al. (2012) carried out a study with the main objective of studying employee job satisfaction. The research involved the crucial problems, faced by employees while working in organizations and found ways to make employees loyal to their organization. The purpose of the research was to elaborate on the key factors which are useful for the satisfaction of the employees i.e., workplace environment, reward and recognition, training and development, and teamwork. These factors help to make the policies effective and through this effectiveness, efficiency takes place in the management process. The research was based on theoretical considerations, a model was proposed linking the employee job satisfaction (EJS) constructs. The survey was conducted in 2012 and covered 200 employees within the territory of Punjab in Pakistan. The result established a strong positive relationship between teamwork and all other factors.

Inayat and Khan (2021) researched to study the effect of job satisfaction on the performance of employees working in private sector organizations in Peshawar, Pakistan. For that purpose, one hundred and eighty employees (N = 180) were selected as a sample from private organizations in Peshawar. An equal number of employees, i.e., (n = 60), were selected through a random sampling method from three types of organizations, viz., hospitals, banks, and universities. A Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ-short form) developed by Weiss et al. (1967) and a self-constructed Performance Evaluation Form (PRF) were used as instruments for the study. Initially, the reliability statistics of both instruments were calculated to know the significance of the scales. According to the findings of the study, the type of occupation has shown a significant correlation with job satisfaction. Similarly, the positive relationship between job satisfaction and the performance of employees was also confirmed.

Methodology

A descriptive cross-sectional research design was used for this investigation. The responders were selected at random from among the numerous corporate divisions, including the procurement, finance, and human resources divisions. Purposive sampling was used to choose these organizations for the investigation. The survey findings were evaluated using SPSS 28.0's simple linear regression analysis. The aim of the study was to investigate the impact of internal auditing on financial performance.

Based on the link between predictors and dependent variables, simple linear regression analysis is the model specification employed in this study endeavor.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \mu \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$Y = f(X)$$

Where Y= Dependent variable represented by financial performance

x_1 = Predictors variable (Internal Audit)

β_0 = Slope or intercept

β_1 = Regression coefficients

μ = Error term

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The data collected from respondents in the various firms under study are presented, analyzed, and interpreted in this part. To meet our goal for this study, the replies were categorized by categorizing them using a Likert scale approach. A study of the structured questionnaire was conducted utilizing social science statistical software (SPSS version 28.0)

Table 1: Response Rate

	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percent
Returned	152	87.86	87.86
Unreturned	21	12.14	100
Total	173	100	

Source: Field Work 2022

One hundred seventy-three (173 copies) of the questionnaires were distributed, but only one hundred and fifty-two (152) of them were returned, and the remaining copies were not. There were 21 unreturned items (21). The following are some of the causes for the unreturned.

- i. A few respondents lost the questionnaire given to them.
- ii. A few respondents reluctantly did not respond to the questionnaire and lastly few others ticked two answers for a question, and this was recorded as a void to avoid incorrect interpretations.

Organizational Salary Structure

The instrument sort to find out about the organizational structure of the firm

Table 2: Organizational salary structure

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Strongly Disagree
I am satisfied with the benefits that are offered in my organization.	47 (30.9%)	69 (45.4%)	24 (15.8%)	12 (7.2%)
I think my base pay is competitive compared to similar positions in other companies.	55 (36.2%)	63 (41.4%)	14 (14.5%)	10 (6.6%)
Educational qualification influences the salary structure of your organization.	53 (34.9%)	64 (42.1%)	23 (15.1%)	12 (7.8%)
Years of experience determine the salary structure of staff in the organization.	41 (26.9%)	66 (43.4%)	31 (20.4%)	14 (9.2%)

Source: Fieldwork 2022

When it came to whether the participants are satisfied with the benefits offered in their organizations, the findings revealed that 31% strongly agreed and 45% agreed. Because a greater % of respondents agreed, this implies that there is clear evidence that the organization salary structure benefits the staff.

The study sought to determine whether the base pay is competitive when compared to similar positions in other companies. According to table 2, 36% of employees strongly agreed that the base pay is competitive when compared to similar positions in other organizations, 41% agreed, 15% were neutral, and 7% strongly disagreed.

Furthermore, 35% of employees strongly agreed that educational qualification influences the salary structure of their organizations. 42% agreed, 15% were neutral, and 8% strongly disagreed that education does not affect the salary structure of the organization.

The study went on to determine whether years of work experience determine the salary structure of the staff in the organization. According to table 2, the majority of respondents (27% strongly agreed, 43% agreed, 20% were neutral, and only 9% strongly disagreed).

Employee Skill

This instrument seeks to find out the employee skill of the respondents.

Table 3: Employee Skill

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Strongly Disagree
Our organization offers enough training opportunities to keep my knowledge and skills up to date.	73 (48%)	62 (40.8)	11 (7.2%)	6 (3.9%)
My job enables me to learn and develop new skills.	55 (36.2)	61 (40.1)	16 (10.5)	20 (13.2%)
My direct manager gives fair and practical feedback to help me improve my work skill.	66 (43.3%)	60 (39.5)	17 (11.2%)	9 (5.9%)
Ongoing training boosts confidence and ensures that employees correctly train especially new team members.	55 (36.2%)	32 (21.1%)	26 (17.1%)	39 (25.7%)

Source: Fieldwork 2022

According to the findings, 48% of respondents strongly agreed, 41% agreed, 7% were neutral, and 4% strongly disagreed that their organization offers enough training opportunities to keep staff knowledge and skills up to date, thereby we organizations promote employee skills.

The results indicate 36% of the participants strongly agreed, 40% agreed, 11% were neutral and 13% strongly disagreed that the Job enables them to learn and develop new skills.

Table 3 shows 43% of the respondents strongly agreed, 40% agreed, 11% were neutral and 6% strongly disagreed that their direct manager gives fair and practical feedback to help them improve their work skills.

From the study 36% of the participants strongly agreed, 21% agreed, 17% were neutral and 26% strongly disagreed that the ongoing training in their organizations boost confidence and ensures that employee correctly trains especially new team members.

Working Condition

This instrument seeks to find out about the working condition of the firms.

Table 4: Indicators of Working Condition

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Strongly Disagree
My work schedule is flexible enough for me to meet my family/personal responsibilities.	73 (48%)	62 (40.8)	11 (7.2%)	6 (3.9%)
People of all cultures and backgrounds are respected and valued here.	55 (36.2)	61 (40.1)	16 (10.5)	20 (13.2%)
Do you feel that your colleagues and managers care about your well-being?	66 (43.3%)	60 (39.5)	17 (11.2%)	9 (5.9%)
Do you feel comfortable asking your manager for support in sustaining a healthy work-life balance?	55 (36.2%)	32 (21.1%)	26 (17.1%)	39 (25.7%)

Source: Fieldwork 2022

According to the findings, 48% of respondents strongly agreed, 41% agreed, 7% were neutral, and 4% strongly disagreed that their work schedule is flexible enough for them to meet their family and personal responsibilities.

The results also indicate 36% of the participants strongly agreed, 40% agreed, 11% were neutral and 13% strongly disagreed that people of all cultures and backgrounds are respected and valued in their organizations.

Table 3 shows 43% of the respondents strongly agreed, 40% agreed, 11% were neutral and 6% strongly disagreed that they feel that their colleagues and managers care about their well-being.

From the study 36% of the participants strongly agreed, 21% agreed, 17% were neutral and 26% strongly disagreed that they feel comfortable asking their manager for support in sustaining a healthy work-life balance.

Hypothesis Testing

Decision Rule: Accept the null hypothesis if the probability value >0.05 otherwise accepts the alternative hypothesis.

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Employee skill has no significant positive effect on the organizational salary structure.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Working conditions have no significant positive effect on the organizational salary structure.

Table 5: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.494 ^a	.722	.689	3.08124
a. Predictors: (Constant), Employee Skill; Working condition				

Model Testing and Interpretation

The model summary above explains the percentage of the dependent variable (organizational Structure), which can be determined by the independent variable (employee skill and working conditions). According to this Table, the dependent variables account for 72.2% (R Square, 0.722) of the independent variable. While the remaining 27.8% can be explained by other factors outside the scope of this model. This implies that employee skill and working conditions have a direct influence on an organizational salary structure. This Pearson correlation coefficient (R) result also showed a positive value of 0.494, which also lends credence to the fact that the predictor variable has a direct relationship with the response variable.

Table 6: ANOVA Table

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	129.014	1	129.014	4.860	.001 ^a
	Residual	3982.249	151	26.548		
	Total	4111.263	152			
a. Dependent Variable: Organizational structure						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Employee skill; Working condition						

The study also conducted an analysis of variance to determine the extent to which the Independent and dependent variable relates with each other, and the result showed that P- the value Obtained (0.001) was lower than the 5% level of significance specified in SPSS software for this analysis, therefore, according to the decision rule, the Alternate hypothesis will be accepted, while the Null hypothesis will be rejected. This implies that employee skill and work condition have a significant influence on the organizational salary structure of the firms studied.

Table 7: Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	18.968	2.415		7.855	.000
	Employee skill	0.318	0.104	0.177	3.057	.019
	Working condition	0.098	0.061	0.005	1.606	.249
a. Dependent Variable: Organizational salary structure						

Simple linear regression analysis was also conducted to determine if the result established by ANOVA statistics is similar to that of the regression coefficient. The result shows that the P-value obtained (i.e., 0.019) for the regression coefficient of employee skill was also lower than the alpha level of significance of 5% specified in SPSS for this analysis therefore, thus, it can be inferred from this result, that the ANOVA Statistic is similar to that of the regression coefficient. Thus, the Alternate Hypothesis will be accepted while the Null Hypothesis will be rejected, which means that employee skill has a significant positive effect on the organizational salary structure.

Also, the result shows that the P-value obtained (i.e., 0.249) for the regression coefficient of working condition was also higher than the alpha level of significance of 5% specified in SPSS for this analysis therefore, thus, it can be inferred from this result. Thus, the Alternate Hypothesis will be rejected while the Null Hypothesis will be accepted, which means that working condition has no significant positive effect on the organizational salary structure of the firms.

Discussion of Results

The result of this study indicates that employee skills will significantly improve the organizational salary structure of organizations. This was confirmed by the result of the statistical analysis which shows that the P-value obtained (0.019) was lower than the significance value of 5% specified in SPSS for this analysis. Similarly, the result of this study indicates that working conditions will not significantly improve the organizational salary structure of the organizations. This was confirmed by the result of the statistical analysis which shows that the P-value obtained (0.249) was higher than the significance value of 5% specified in SPSS for this analysis.

Conclusion

Based on the study, the effect of job evaluation techniques on employees' salary structure in organizations in Nigeria. Employee skills have significantly positively improved the organizational salary structure of organizations. While working conditions have insignificantly improved the organizational salary structure of the organizations. We concluded that job evaluation techniques have a significant effect on employees' salary structure in organizations in Nigeria.

Recommendation

We recommended that organizations in Nigeria and beyond should endeavor to significantly improve the organizational job evaluation techniques since it has a significant effect on employees' salary structure in organizations in Nigeria.

The following recommendation is also given:

- i. Employees should endeavor to improve their skills it has a significant effect on an organizational salary structure.
- ii. Better working conditions should be provided for the employees to improve their skills.

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